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ASSESSMENT, EVALUATION, AND ANALYSIS OF ADOLESCENT GIRLS' KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PRACTICE ON URINARY TRACT INFECTION IN TUMKUR CITY

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ABSTRACT

Background: The kidney, ureters, bladder, and urethra constitute the urinary system. UTI is an infection of the urinary tract caused by bacteria such as *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumonia* and some others. Urinary tract infections (UTIs) are the second most common type of infection in the body. **Objectives:** To assess the knowledge, attitude and practice about UTI in adolescent girls, to educate girls on UTI and to assess the impact of education by post questionnaires. **Methodology:** The study was a prospective, interventional study that lasted six months and was divided into three parts, with some inclusion and exclusion criteria. Pre- test and post-test questionnaires were used to collect data from adolescent girls at selected PU colleges in Tumkur, and students were educated by utilizing PIL and power point presentations. **Result:** The aggregate number of students who participated in the study was 406, consisting 119 by a Private PU College for Women and 287 from a Government PU College for Women. The participants' mean pre-test score was 52.74 %, which increased to 75.55 % in the post-test. The pre-test score of knowledge, attitude and practice seem to have been 44.02 %, 61.57 %, and 68.41 %, and the post-test scores which was increased to 71.15 %, 91.13 %, and 87.8 % respectively. **Conclusion:** The study shows there is improvement in basic aspects of the topic after educating. Hence educating adolescents on various infections and encouraging them to modify their life style plays a vital role to lead healthy life.

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INTRODUCTION

The urinary system is responsible for the formation, storage, and excretion of waste from the body. The kidneys, ureters, bladder, and urethra are the organs that compose the urinary system^[1]. Urinary tract infection refers to an infection in any part of the urinary tract^[2]. Cystitis (infection of the urinary bladder), urethritis (infection of the urethra), prostatitis (infection of the prostate), and Pyelonephritis (infection of the kidneys) are the different types of infections^[1]. UTI is a relatively prevalent ailment that affects both men and women of all ages. UTI is more common in women than in males due to a variety of clinical reasons, including hormonal changes, behavioral patterns, and physical abnormalities^[3] such as women having a shorter urethra than men, allowing germs to move quickly from the anus to the vagina and then to the bladder^[4]. In India, approximately 50-60% of women^[5] and 12% of men will have at least one symptomatic UTI over their lives, with approximately 40% of affected women experiencing recurrent UTI. The prevalence of UTI in pregnant women, including both symptomatic and asymptomatic infection, has been found to range from 3% to 24%^[6]. Gram negative enteric bacteria such as *E coli*, *Proteus species* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and also gram positive cocci such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus agalactiae*, and *Staphylococcus saprophyticus*, are the most common micro organisms that cause UTI^[7]. Filthy restrooms, the use of unsanitary napkins, unsanitary practices during menstruation, and wiping from back to front are just a few of the ways these microorganisms can cause or spread illnesses^[8]. Burning sensation during micturition, frequent or severe urge to urinate, cloudy-dark-bloody or unusual smelling urine, tiredness or shakiness, fever and chills, pus cells in urine, back pain, nausea, and vomiting all are signs and symptoms of urinary tract infection^[5]. Predisposing variables for UTI include age, sex, metabolic problems, intervention such as catheterization and any surgical procedure^[9], pregnancy, and anatomical and functional abnormalities of the urinary tract. If the infection is not treated, it can cause problems like Pyelonephritis, which causes chronic kidney damage, sepsis, which can be fatal, and urethral constriction (stricture) in men^[10]. There are several measures that can be taken to prevent the occurrence of UTI such as stay hydrated i.e. intake of large volume of water helps to dilute and remove pathogen from urinary tract by increasing the rate of urination, follow good hygienic practices of the genital areas, wiping from front to back, avoiding tight fitting clothes, prefer cotton underwear, consuming cranberry juice which helps to increase antibacterial activity of urine by acidifying^[11], drying under garments under direct sunlight, emptying bladder completely, keeping toilets clean are some of the simple and effective ways to prevent UTI^[8].

Vaccines:

Several vaccination approaches have been explored in the last 20 years, the use of heat killed whole bacteria, bacterial cell extracts and purified UPEC-associated virulence factor includes in these category^[12, 13].

Both oral and vaginal formulations have been proposed, the most widely used oral formulation is Uro-Vaxon or OM-89^[14]. Due to lack of sufficient evidence vaginal vaccines are not clinically practical^[15].

UTI's were found to be more common in older and middle-aged females, educating at the level of adolescent may help to reduce the impact of these infections.

OBJECTIVES

- 1) To assess the knowledge, attitude and practice about UTI in adolescent girls.
- 2) To educate girls on UTI.
- 3) To assess the impact of education by post questionnaires.

METHODOLOGY

Study design: Prospective interventional study

Study site: Selected PU colleges in Tumkur city

Duration of study: Six months

Sample size: 406

Source of data: The data was collected from adolescent girls of selected PU colleges in Tumkur city

Materials used:

- Questionnaires: Pre test and Post test
- Patient information leaflets
- Power point presentations

Study criteria:

Inclusion criteria

- Adolescent girls
- Being willing to participate in study

Exclusion criteria

- Presence of co morbid conditions
- Psychiatric subjects
- Subjects who had unsuccessful urinary tract surgery in the past

Phases of study

Phase 1: Pre test

Data was gathered by conducting pre-test and delivering questionnaires to assess adolescent girl students' awareness about UTI.

Phase 2: Education

The study population was educated by power point presentation and PIL was provided to each student which contains information about UTI symptoms, causes and prevention.

Phase 3: Post test

Follow up was done and data was collected by post test questionnaires which gives the information about knowledge of study population after educating.

This prospective interventional study was conducted in selected PU colleges of Tumkur city by taking the permission from the Principals of both the colleges and preceded further. The study was conducted in three phases, the first phase was pre-test in which the study population was given a set of pre-test questionnaires to assess the knowledge they have regarding the study topic. Then the second phase is educating the students about the topic which is most important. This phase is not only important to complete the study but to lead a healthy life by our adolescents. The second phase was carried out by explaining Parts of urinary tract, what is UTI, causes and symptoms, reason for why UTI is more common in women than in men, and the ways to prevent UTI through power point presentation by common language which was helpful to reach all the study population. In this phase students were provided with Patient Information Leaflet which was both in English and regional language, as PIL helps to recall the points that were spoken during presentation. The gap of around three months was given to include or follow the hygienic practices in their daily life which reflects in answering post-test questionnaires of third phase.

Ethical approval:

With prior clearance from the College administration and the Institutional Ethics Committee on 27/12/2019 with IEC Ref number: SSCPT/SHRC/PPD/2019-20, this study was conducted and completed

RESULT

The total number of people that took part in the study was 406. Private PU College for Women has 119 students while Government PU College for Women has 287 students. The pre-test and post-test questionnaire answers were revised and entered into MS Excel. The results of the pre-test and post-test were categorized and the results are listed below:

Figure 1: Distribution of mean scores.

The students' mean pre-test score was 52.74%, and their post-test score was 75.55%, indicating an improvement in knowledge, attitude, and practice with the topic. (Figure 1).

Table 1: Branch wise distribution.

	Pre test	Post test
PCMB	53.96%	77.2%
Commerce, Arts	52.14%	74.73%

Figure 2: Branch wise distribution.

In the pre-test, PCMB and commerce, arts students had nearly identical knowledge, and they had equally enhanced their knowledge of UTI after being educated, as evidenced by the post-test. (Table 1 and Figure 2).

Table 2: Method of drying undergarments.

Response	Pre test	Post test
Under direct sunlight	320	395
In shade	56	5
Under fan	30	6

The improper drying of underwear, such as in the shade, beneath a fan, and so on, contributed to the development of UTI. Students were taught the importance of drying underwear under sunlight. (Table 2)

Table 3: Response for method of perineal washing.

Response	Pre test	Post test
From anus to urethra (back to front)	195	20
From urethra to anus (front to back)	146	313
Both	65	73

We discovered that pupils were bathing their perineum incorrectly. However, following education, there has been a rise in the right practice of perineal cleansing. (Table 3).

Figure 3: Response for duration of keeping a napkin during menstruation.

Table 4: Response for duration of keeping a napkin during menstruation.

	Pre test	Post test
< 4 hours	71.42%	85.71%
4-8 hours	24.63%	12.31%
>8 hours	3.9%	1.97%

During the pre-test, it was discovered that the majority of students were retaining napkins for an extended period of time. This was remedied by education. (Figure 3; Table 4).

Table 5: Response for type of napkin using during menstruation.

Response	Pre test	Post test
House made napkins (cloth)	51	6
Sanitary napkins	355	400

Most of the students were using homemade napkins such as cloth during the menstruation. (Table 5).

Figure 4: Knowledge about UTI.

Overall knowledge about UTI among students in pre test was only 44.02% which was increased to 71.15% in post test. (Figure 4)

Table 6: Scores between colleges.

	Pre test	Post test
Private college for women	46.28%	72.33%
Government college for women	55.42%	76.89%

Figure 5: Scores between colleges.

In both the pre-test and post-test, the results showed that students of Government College for Women had better knowledge about UTI than students of Private College for Women. (Table 6 and Figure 5).

Figure 6: Scores of practice.

The proper practice regarding UTI in the pre-test was 68.41%. The practice score climbed to 87.8% after intervention, indicating that educating college students is crucial in reducing Urinary Tract Infections. (Figure 6).

Table 7: Final comparison.

	Pre test	Post test
Knowledge	44.02%	71.15%
Attitude	61.57%	91.13%
Practice	68.41%	87.8%

Figure 7: Final comparison.

The above pie chart shows the comparison of KAP between Pre test and Post test. By the evidence of this pie chart we can see that after educating the students regarding UTI they have improved in all aspect of the topic. (Table 7, Figure 7)

DISCUSSION

UTI is more frequent in females than in males, contributing to female morbidity at all ages. In India, the National Family Health Survey (NFHS) 2000 revealed a 16.6% prevalence of UTI among adolescent females (10-19 years) and a 5-10% chance of acquiring bacteremia in adolescent girls. Ignoring a UTI can lead to kidney failure, septicemia, bacterial endocarditis, prostatitis, and infertility in the long run.

By delivering PIL and a presentation on UTI, the study aimed to raise awareness of the many elements of UTI among adolescent girls. Because UTI is more common in adolescent girls and young females than in males, the study focused on adolescent girls.

The study comprised 406 individuals, and the known characteristics of UTI among college students were minimal, as determined by the pre-test score. The post-test score improved noticeably after intervention. The pre-test mean score distribution was 52.74%, which climbed to 75.55% in the post-test. Many students engaged in unsanitary activities such as leaving napkins out for more than 6 hours, using cloth as napkins, employing the incorrect way of perineal cleansing, drying underwear in the shade or under a fan, and so on. These incorrect habits were remedied by offering PIL and giving a lecture on the matter, which helped them comprehend the ramifications of their actions.

Similar study was conducted by Anjaly Vijayan, et al. among adolescent girls in Chitradurga city. The sample size was 467; pre test and post test were conducted. The knowledge on UTI in pre test was $4.78(\pm 1.6)$ had increased to $10.8(\pm 1.301)$ in post test after the intervention. This interventional study shows a gradual improvement in the knowledge, attitude and practice regarding UTI in adolescent girls.

CONCLUSION

To establish a healthy nation, many training programs on diverse themes for adolescent students are needed and important to improve knowledge and the ability to follow healthy behaviors in order to improve the quality of life.

Future research: This study can be further carried out to find prevalence of UTI in different life stages such as adolescents, geriatrics, pregnant women.

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ABBREVIATIONS

UTI	- Urinary Tract infection
E coli	- Escherichia coli
PIL	- Patient Information Leaflet
KAP	- Knowledge, Attitude, Practice
PU	- Pre University
NFHS	- National Family Health Survey
UPEC	- Uropathogenic E coli
MS Excel	- Microsoft Excel
IEC	- Institutional Ethics Committee

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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